

Silver catalysed Oxidation of *cis*-(Diglycinato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) Ion by Potassium Peroxydisulphate in Aqueous Perchlorate Medium

PRAKASH MOHANTY^{a*}, NIGAMANANDA DAS^b and JASHODA KUMARI DEI^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-751 004

^bRegional Research Laboratory, Bhubaneswar-751 013

Manuscript received 8 February 1993, revised 7 May 1993, accepted 14 May 1993

Kinetics of metal ion catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of amino acids^{1,2}, coordinated formate³ and oxalate⁴ have been studied. Recently peroxy-disulphate oxidation of coordinated isothiocyanate has also been studied⁵. However, oxidation of glycinate bound to cobalt(III) centre has not been attempted. In this paper we report the silver catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of *cis*-(diglycinato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) in acid medium.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic results can be summarised as follows. (i) The reaction was found to be fractional order (0.5) in [oxidant]. With [complex] = 2×10^{-3} , $[Ag^+] = 10^{-3}$ and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the plot of $10^4 k_{obs}$ versus $[S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1/2}$ is linear (Table 1) when $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ is changed from 1.0×10^{-2} to $5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (ii) under pseudo-first order condition, i.e. [oxidant] = 0.01, $[H^+] = 0.1$, $[Ag^+] = 0.001$ and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the reaction follows first order kinetics in [complex]. Under these conditions, the first order rate constants remain constant $(2.0 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at different initial [complex] in the range 0.002–0.006 mol dm^{-3} . (iii) Pseudo-first order rate constants were determined at various $[Ag^+]$. The plot of rate constants against different $[Ag^+]$ was linear (figure not shown) and did not pass through origin indicating that catalysed and uncatalysed oxidation take place simultaneously. (iv) The rate constant decreased with increase in $[H^+]$. For example, under the conditions [complex] = 0.002, [oxidant] = 0.01,

$[Ag^+] = 0.001$ and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the $10^4 k_{obs}$ at 60° decreased from 2.04 ± 0.02 to $0.99 \pm 0.12 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and from 1.10 ± 0.01 to $0.53 \pm 0.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively, for the catalysed and uncatalysed path, when $[H^+]$ was increased from 0.1 to 0.6 mol dm^{-3} . (v) Activation parameters for the silver catalysed reaction were calculated by determining the $[H^+]$ dependence at four different temperatures (323, 328, 333 and 338 K) and at $[Ag^+] = 0.001$, $[S_2O_8^{2-}] = 0.01$, [complex] = 0.002 and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for the silver catalysed reaction were found to be $101 \pm 7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-13.3 \pm 1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1).

Based on the above facts probable mechanism may be delineated as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Under pseudo-first order condition of [oxidant]_T the rate law will be given by equation (1),

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1[H^+] + Kk_2[Ag^+]}{[H^+] + K[Ag^+]} \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR SILVER CATALYSED PEROXYDISULPHATE OXIDATION OF *cis*-(DIGLYCINATO)BIS-(ETHYLENEDIAMINE)COBALT(III) ION AT VARYING $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ AND $[Ag^+]$

[Complex] = 2.0×10^{-3} , $[H^+] = 0.1$, $l = 1.0$ mol dm ⁻³ , Temp = 60°		
$\times 10^2 [S_2O_8^{2-}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^3 [Ag^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹
1.0	1.0	2.04 ± 0.02
1.5	1.0	2.07 ± 0.02
2.0	1.0	2.09 ± 0.01
2.5	1.0	2.14 ± 0.05
3.0	1.0	2.68 ± 0.14
3.5	1.0	2.90 ± 0.04
4.0	1.0	3.45 ± 0.16
4.5	1.0	3.84 ± 0.22
5.0	1.0	3.90 ± 0.12
1.0	1.2	2.22 ± 0.10
1.0	1.4	2.56 ± 0.20
1.0	1.6	2.69 ± 0.14
1.0	1.8	2.80 ± 0.09
1.0	2.0	3.07 ± 0.09

Equation (1) can be linearised to equation (2) for which $k'_{obs} = k_{obs}$ at $[Ag^+] = 0$,

$$\frac{(k_{obs} - k'_{obs}) [H^+]}{[Ag^+]} = Kk_2 - Kk_{obs} \quad (2)$$

The values of equilibrium constant (K) and k_2 obtained from the slopes and intercepts of $(k_{obs} - k'_{obs}) [H^+]/[Ag^+]$ vs k_{obs} plots (see eqn. 2) are collected in Table 2. It is interesting to note that the equilibrium constant values decreased and k_2 values increased with the increase of temperature from 323 to 338 K. The linear plots of $(k_{obs} - k'_{obs}) [H^+]/[Ag^+]$ at all the temperature also supported the proposed mechanism (figure not shown). The formation of the binuclear complex between the title complex and Ag^+ as proposed in the mechanism is visualised from the O.D. vs λ plot (Fig. 1), when O.D. is found to increase at a given wavelength for the same [complex] in the presence of $[Ag^+]$. The formation of binuclear complex (1 : 1) is further evident from the Job's curve (Fig. 2), a plot of $\Delta O.D.$ (difference of optical densities of $Co^{III} + Ag^I$ and Co^{III} alone at 360 nm) against mole fraction of ligand.

TABLE 2—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR SILVER CATALYSED PEROXYDISULPHATE OXIDATION OF *cis*-[Co(en)₂(glyH)₂]³⁺ IN AQUEOUS PERCHLORATE MEDIUM

Temp. (°C)	50.0 ± 0.1	55.0 ± 0.1	60.0 ± 0.1	65.0 ± 0.1
$K (\times 10^{-2})$	5.0 ± 0.04	4.2 ± 0.02	2.01 ± 0.05	1.25 ± 0.01
$k_2 (\times 10^4 s^{-1})$	0.74 ± 0.03	1.05 ± 0.07	2.36 ± 0.11	3.72 ± 0.15
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	101 ± 7			
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-13.3 ± 2			

Fig. 1. Plots of O.D. vs λ at pH = 4.62 ± 0.01 : (a) [complex] = 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ (b) [complex] = 2×10^{-3} and $[Ag^+] = 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ and (c) $[Ag^+] = 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³

Fig. 2. Plot of $\Delta O.D.$ vs $[Co^{III}]/[Co^{III}] + [Ag^I]$ at pH = 2.40 ± 0.01; $\Delta O.D.$ = $[O.D. Co^{III} + O.D. Ag^I] - O.D. Co^{III}$.

The proposed reaction scheme for Ag^+ catalysed oxidation suggests that the binuclear species is the reaction intermediates. Presumably silver in such species exists in +2 state and induced inner-sphere oxidation of the coordinated glycinate. The observed order of the reaction with respect to $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ being 0.5, $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ produced from the thermal dissociation of the oxidant ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-} \rightleftharpoons 2 \text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) appears to be the oxidising species. It is worth noting that under identical conditions the value of k_2 ($(2.36 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) at 60° is about half of that reported for free glycine ($k_2 = 5.12 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, calculated from the data in the temperature range $30\text{--}45^\circ$)¹, indicating that oxidation rate of glycine slows down on being coordinated to cobalt(III) centre. This is further supported by higher activation enthalpy ($101 \pm 7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) for the catalysed path (k_2 path) of the title complex than that of free glycine ($\sim 60 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$)¹.

Experimental

The title complex was prepared by the reported method⁶. The purity of the complex was checked by cobalt analysis and uv-visible spectral data. Potassium peroxydisulphate, perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate used were of A.R. grade. All the solutions were prepared using double-distilled water. The reaction was studied under pseudo-first order conditions and the reaction was monitored by following the decrease of absorbance due to complex with time at 500 nm using a JASCO 7800 spectrophotometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated by suitable computer program which made a least-squares fit of absorbance versus time data.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by withdrawing a definite volume of reaction mixture at the beginning and after five half-lives and then they were allowed to pass through a cation exchange Dowex 50W-X8 resin column separately. The cationic species such as Ag^+ , Na^+ ,

$\text{cis}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{glyH})_2]^{3+}$ and Co^{2+} were retained in the resin column. The unreacted peroxydisulphate in the eluted solution was estimated iodometrically by Frigerio's method⁷, using phosphate buffer. Accounting for the Ag^+ catalysed decomposition of peroxydisulphate in aqueous solution and determining the amount of cobalt(II) formed by Kitson's method⁹, it was possible to determine the stoichiometry of the reaction. The results show that the complex reacted with peroxydisulphate in 1 : 1 molar ratio.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. A. C. Dash for many valuable suggestions and keen interest.

References

1. G. CHANDRA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 773.
2. M. G. R. REDDY, B. SETHURAM and T. N. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 31.
3. R. K. NANDA, A. C. DASH and G. C. PRADHAN, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1990, **15**, 160; N. K. MOHANTY and P. C. RATH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 56.
4. R. K. NANDA, A. C. DASH and P. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 11.
5. V. HOLBA, O. GRANCICOVA and A. PAULENOVA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 121; V. HOLBA and J. BENKO, "Proceedings of Conference on Coordination Chemistry", 1987, p. 93; V. HOLBA, J. BENKO, O. GRANCICOVA and O. VOLAROVA, *Chem. Pap.*, 1989, **43**, 113 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, **110**, 199955).
6. R. K. NANDA, A. C. DASH and P. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 392.
7. N. A. FRIGERIO, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 412.
8. M. KIMURA, T. KAWAJIRI and M. TANIDA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 726.
9. R. K. KITSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 664.

